

Primary Curriculum Development History of Elementary Curriculum Development in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Education continues to develop over time, aiming to improve the quality of education itself. This article was created so that readers better understand the development of the curriculum in Indonesia from time to time which underwent changes starting from the 1947 1952 1964 1966 1998 1975 1984 1994 1999 2004-2006 2003 curriculum until independence of learning. In this article we use several methods to search for material that will be included in the article, namely data collection methods which include collecting data from several books, articles and journals as well as collecting data from the internet

INTRODUCTION

Education is something that every human being must have, because education helps humans to develop in various ways. In education there is something called curriculum. Curriculum is a tool used to achieve educational goals and as a reference in the implementation of education. Curriculum shows the basis or outlook on life of a nation. The form of life that will be used by that nation will be determined by the curriculum used in that country.

Along with developments over time, the curriculum in Indonesia continues to change from time to time with the aim of improving the quality of education in Indonesia. The existence of this curriculum has a significant influence on the quality of education in Indonesia. Therefore, through this article, the author explains in more depth and detail the development of the education curriculum in Indonesia from time to time.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This curriculum change occurs in line with changes in the political, social, cultural, economic and science and technology systems in national and state life. The educational curriculum needs to be developed dynamically in accordance with the demands and changes of the times in which the curriculum is applied. The national curriculum in Indonesia is based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. The differences are in the educational objectives and approaches to realizing them (Wahyuni, 2015: 232).

METHODOLOGY

In this article, we use data collection methods. Data collection methods are the methods used to collect and analyze data. By collecting data, researchers can answer certain questions, test hypotheses, and assess results. Both qualitative and quantitative research each have different data collection methods. This method can be chosen according to needs. Researchers can also carry out several data collection methods at once.

Data collection steps will start from determining the information you want to collect, determining the time period, determining the data collection method, carrying out data collection, and ending with data analysis.

This article also uses the Documentation method, a method used to obtain data and information in book form. Archives, written numbers and images in the form of reports and information that can support this activity. In this case, the analyzer will collect documents related to the discussion that will be discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

History of Curriculum Development

The curriculum in Indonesia after Indonesia's independence in 1945 has undergone 9 changes, including in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1975, 1984, 1994, 2004, 2006 and 2013. In contrast to that, the Ministry of Education and Culture explained the history of curriculum development, namely: Curriculum development consists of the first curriculum 1947, second curriculum 1954, third curriculum 1968 curriculum, fourth curriculum 1973 (Pioneer School Development Project), fifth curriculum 1975, sixth curriculum 1984, seventh curriculum 1994, eighth curriculum 1997 (revised curriculum 1994), nine curriculum 2004 (Competency Based Curriculum), tenth curriculum 2006 (Education Unit Level Curriculum), eleventh curriculum 2013.6F 7 Changes in orientation, design, models and so on with the main aim of improving the quality and quality of national education and aligning it with existing education in world.

A. Old Order Education Curriculum (1947-1965)

The curriculum during the old order was divided into three curricula, namely:
1. Curriculum 1947

At the beginning of independence, the term curriculum was known in Dutch as "Leer Plan" which means lesson plan. In this curriculum there are two main things, namely a list of subjects, teaching hours and Teaching Program Outlines (GBPP). The 1947 lesson plan was a replacement for the Dutch colonial education system and began to be implemented in schools in 1950. This curriculum prioritizes character education, awareness of state and society, subject matter is related to daily activities, attention is focused on educational and physical arts (Wicaksono, 2018: 53).

The implementation of the 1947 curriculum did not emphasize cognitive aspects but only prioritized character education such as building a sense of nationalism. The next aspect is the main objective in the 1947 Lesson Plan curriculum. The program structure in the 1947 Lesson Plan is divided into two parts, namely the program structure using regional languages and Indonesian. The subject structure in the 1947 Lesson Plan curriculum is separate or in the curriculum context it is called a separated curriculum. Menurut Wirianto (2014:140), Berikut ini ciri-ciri kurikulum 1947:

- a. Nature of the curriculum separate subject curriculum (1946- 1947).
- b. Using Indonesian as the language of instruction at school.
- c. The educational level has a different number of subjects: People's School (SR) - 16 fields of study, SMP-17 fields of study and SMA majoring in B19 fields of study.

2. 1952 Curriculum "1952 Decomposed Lesson Plan"

In 1952 improvements were made to the curriculum in Indonesia which became known as the 1952 curriculum. This curriculum was more detailed in each subject which was then given the name "1952 Decomposed Lesson Plan" and did not yet use the term curriculum. The 1952 curriculum framework was relatively the same as the 1947 curriculum. However, the national education system had become the goal of 1945. UU no. 4 of 1950 concerning the basics of education and teaching in schools influenced the emergence of the 1950 curriculum.

The 1952 curriculum focuses on the Pancawardhana program which includes creativity, taste, character, work and morals. Subjects have been classified into five groups of study areas, namely, moral, intelligence, emotional/artistic, personality, skills, and physical (Asri, 2017: 196). This curriculum implements a community-oriented curriculum so that after completing their education they can immediately work. The weakness of the 1952 curriculum is that this curriculum only aims at the national education system not being able to reach all regions of Indonesia.

3. Curriculum in Indonesia in 1964

The curriculum in Indonesia in 1964 underwent further refinement. The concepts of active, creative and productive learning were issues developed in the 1964 Education Plan. This concept requires every school to guide children to be able to think of their own problem solving solutions to various existing problems. Thus, it can be understood that the curriculum concept in this era is more about how students are active, creative and productive in finding solutions to various problems that are developing and existing in society.

The learning method used in the 1964 curriculum is a method called guided mutual cooperation. Apart from that, the krida day was set on Saturday by the government. Krida Day means that on this day students are given the freedom to practice various activities tailored to their individual interests and talents. Such as cultural activities, arts, sports and various forms of games. The development of this curriculum can be said to be perfect because it has touched three important aspects of students, namely cognitive, affective and psychomotor development. In the 1964 curriculum there were more efforts to develop potential and practical education, no longer just theory (Sukatin & Pahmi, 2020: 89). Similar to the previous curriculum, this curriculum also focuses on developing Pancawardhana which includes creativity, taste, character, work and morals. Subjects have also been classified into five groups of study areas, namely, morals, intelligence, emosional, keprigelan, skills and physicality (Wahyuni, 2015:235).

B. New Order Period (1966-1998)

1. 1968 Curriculum

The political nature was closely attached to the initial emergence of the 1968 curriculum, replacing the 1964 curriculum which was imaged as the result of the "Old Order" government. If seen from the objective aspect, efforts to increase feelings of love for the country, be physically strong and healthy, increase intelligence and physical skills, morals, character and religious beliefs are emphasized more in the 1968 curriculum.

The 1968 curriculum is an embodiment of the implementation of the 1945 Constitution. The subject matter is theoretical. The content of education aims at activities to increase intelligence and skills, as well as maintaining a healthy and strong physique (Alhamuddin, 2014:51). At this time students only act as passive individuals, just memorizing existing theories without any application of these theories. Practically, this curriculum emphasizes the formation of students only from an intellectual perspective.

2. 1975 Curriculum

National development was the background to the birth of the 1975 curriculum as a result of the many changes that occurred, especially since 1969. Many factors influenced government programs and policies which resulted in these reforms. The 1975 curriculum is a curriculum that is centralized or created by the central government and schools only implement it. The 1975 curriculum has the principle that the aim of education must be effective and efficient. The 1975 curriculum received a lot of criticism from implementers in the field. Teachers are kept busy writing details of what will be achieved from each learning activity.

3. 1984 Curriculum

The 1975 curriculum was deemed not to be in accordance with the needs of society at that time, so a new curriculum was formed, namely the 1984 curriculum. The special characteristic of this curriculum is its teaching approach which is centered on students through active student learning or often referred to as CBSA (Active Student Learning Method). . The delivery of material is not just a lecture, field methods have also begun to be used to make learning more effective and efficient in achieving lesson objectives.

Active Student Learning is expected to be able to implement the process of students' intellectual emotional involvement in learning activities which allows for: Assimilation processes/cognitive experiences which enable the formation of knowledge, action processes/direct experiences, skills, appreciation processes and internalization of values (Wicaksono, 2018:57).

4. 1994 Curriculum

Created as a refinement of the 1984 curriculum. The 1994 curriculum was implemented in accordance with Law no. 2 of 1989 concerning the National Education System which had an impact on changing the semester system to a quarterly system. Teaching objectives emphasize understanding concepts and problem solving and problem solving skills.

There are prominent characteristics of the 1994 curriculum according to Imron (2018:21), including the following: 1. Using a quarterly system. 2. The lesson material is quite dense. 3. Implement one curriculum system for all students throughout Indonesia. 4. Mathematics and language lessons dominate (Indonesian and English), minimal art and material lessons. 5. PMP (Pancasila Moral Education) was changed to PPKn (Pancasila and Citizenship Education).

C. Educational Curriculum During the Reform Order (1999-Present)

1. Competency Based Curriculum (2004)

This curriculum is better known as the Competency Based Curriculum because schools are given the authority to prepare the desired syllabus according to the school's needs. Competency-based education focuses on developing the ability to carry out tasks in accordance with predetermined performance standards, so that students can feel the results, in the form of mastery of a certain set of competencies. KBK is expected to be able to develop students' knowledge, understanding, abilities, values, attitudes and interests so that they can do things responsibly (Wirianto, 2014: 146).

The following are the main characteristics of KBK: Emphasizes student achievement of competency, not completion of material. The curriculum can be replaced or changed according to student potential. Student-centered learning. Orientation to process and results. Using diverse and contextual approaches and methods. Teachers are not the only source of knowledge. Textbooks are not the only source of learning. Lifelong learning. Learn to know. Learn to do. Learn to be yourself. Learn to live in diversity.

2. Education (KTSP) or the 2006

curriculum was prepared to carry out the mandate stated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System and Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation no. 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards. The implementation of KTSP refers to the Minister of National Education Regulation (Permendiknas) Number 24 of 2006 concerning the implementation of Content Standards (SI) and Graduate Competency Standards (SKL) which are determined by the school principal after taking into account the considerations of the school committee. The implementation of this curriculum is completely handed over to schools, which means there is no intervention from the Education Service or the National Education Department (Manurung, 2019: 93).

In the 2006 curriculum there are a number of subjects and knowledge that students must take to reach a certain level (promote) or to obtain a diploma. The 2006 Curriculum focuses on plans regarding objectives, content, learning materials used as guidelines for teaching and learning activities to achieve educational goals (Saffina et al, 2020: 57). The following are Content Standards (SI) which are guidelines for developing the Education Unit Level Curriculum which contain: Basic framework and structure of the Curriculum, Learning Load, KTSP developed at the education unit level, and Education Calendar.

Graduate Competency Standards (SKL) are used to determine student graduation. SKL includes competencies for all subjects. SKL objectives are adjusted to the level.

3. 2013 Curriculum

The 2013 curriculum is a character-based curriculum with the aim of improving the quality of educational processes and outcomes that focus on students' noble character and morals in accordance with the Graduate Competency Standards (SKL) in educational units. Through the 2013 curriculum, the government hopes that students will be able to increase knowledge, apply moral values and noble morals so that they can be realized in everyday life (Kosassy, 2017: 82).

The 2013 curriculum policy changes contain four changes to the curriculum, namely, Graduate Competency Standards (SKL), Content Standards (SI), Process Standards and Assessment Standards. The 2013 curriculum policy changes have an impact on four learning models in the form of thematic-integrative, scientific approach, *strategi aktif*, and authentic assessment which aims to prepare future generations of Indonesians who are creative, innovative, productive and affective so they can bring the Indonesian nation forward in the future (Machali, 2014: 87).

The 2013 curriculum is a form of progress over time, where the curriculum is in line with existing developments. Currently, technology has developed rapidly and the curriculum has entered a new realm, namely, combining educational concepts and advances in science and technology. Even though there are still many obstacles faced in its implementation, it can be believed that this will be overcome if the development of the 2013 curriculum is carried out well and correctly.

Primary School Curriculum Policy on Freedom to Learn One of the discourses echoed by the Minister of Education and Culture, Nadiem Makarim, is freedom to learn. Three other policies, namely starting in 2021, there will be no national exams and they will be replaced with minimum competency assessments and character surveys carried out in the middle of the school level, simplification of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP), and regulations for accepting new students (Sularto, 2020: 14). According to Yoga (2020: 14), freedom to learn can be understood as freedom to think, freedom to create, and respecting or responding to changes that occur (having adaptability). According to Priyatma (2020: 6), this concept was born because education had lost its fundamental orientation, namely the development of courage and independence of thought, the absence of the need and courage to think independently. The enthusiasm for learning is a self-attitude and mood that is positively correlated with curiosity, self-confidence and optimism. Learning events will develop if the world of education is able to foster freedom to think and try as well as openness to accepting failure or mistakes.

What are the implications of the concept of "freedom to learn" in its implementation in elementary schools? In this context, there are several things that need to be studied further, namely simplification of the curriculum, implementation of national exams, simplification of lesson plans, and the teaching profession. The first is curriculum simplification. The main aim of simplifying the curriculum is to make the curriculum more relevant so that the

competencies of educational graduates are in line with current and future demands.

Curriculum simplification must be oriented and envision a future that is increasingly disruptive in all walks of life (Suyanto, 2019: 6). The curriculum which has been a guide to educational practice has been simplified. Complaints about the burden of the curriculum have long been felt. Geographical factors and the ability of educators (teachers) as well as the area where the school is administered have been present in the implementation of the curriculum, between the curriculum on paper and the actual curriculum implemented in schools.

Second, holding national exams. So far, national exams have been felt by schools to be difficult, not only for students but also teachers. Schools spend a lot of time preparing for national exams, especially before they are implemented. Carrying out educational practice in accordance with the curriculum is already a heavy burden, let alone achieving national standards for learning success. It is appropriate that the education minister's decision abolished national exams, replacing them with competency and character assessments.

Third, simplification of the RPP. If the previous RP consisted of 10-13 components, then in independent learning it has been changed to only 3 components, namely learning objectives, learning activities, and learning assessment (Kristiana, 2020: 14). This policy is truly in favor of teachers who have long been burdened with making RPPs that take pages for a long time. However, according to Suyanto (2020: 6) if the RPP is only one page then teachers are not sure they can make it well without mastering the essence of the RPP. Furthermore, Kristiana (2020: 11) sees that the aim of preparing lesson plans is to give teachers the opportunity to plan interactive learning, to design learning according to student needs, to simplify the implementation of the learning process, and to facilitate the implementation of learning evaluations. In this context, freedom to learn according to Lie (2020: 6) helps teachers and students achieve happiness. Teachers find joy in teaching and students find happiness in learning. Teachers and students don't feel it trapped in the learning process. Fourth, the teaching profession. Teaching as a profession that has long been recognized as the key to education and learning remains a strategic and important factor. Teachers are no longer the only source of knowledge but as colleagues who together with students seek and find knowledge. However, teachers are assumed to be better prepared. Because of that. It is important that teachers have knowledge and skills as educators, not just speakers (Sularto, 2020: 15). According to Abduhzen (2020: 6), the implications of the concept of independent learning in curriculum development, especially curriculum implementation in elementary schools, include objectives, flexibility and usefulness. Related to goal orientation, independent learning will be a goal-oriented process. Learning achievement standards are very clear in the 2013 Curriculum. However, teachers are free to achieve these standards so that teachers develop interaction patterns that suit the conditions of each class.

This is where the teacher's ability to improvise is required so that learning is more effective, enriched, interesting and enjoyable. In the context of flexibility,

when carrying out independent learning, teachers can flexibly choose and determine the strategies or methods used; but when the learning process encounters obstacles, with a sense of freedom and creativity the teacher can look for and choose other strategies or approaches to achieve the goal. In the usability framework, when teachers and policy makers plan a curriculum, according to Minister Nadiem Makarim, it must be filtered with one question, "What is the use of this for students in the future?" So when the teacher prepares a lesson plan by including core and basic competencies, make sure the teacher thinks about its usefulness for students in the future. This means that teachers do not just prepare lesson plans as a "ceremony" but always think about the benefits for the students' future.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The history of curriculum development reflects the evolution of education over time. This article explains how values, teaching methods, and educational priorities have changed with the changing needs of society and the world of work. From traditional approaches to more context-specific curriculum models, these developments reflect efforts to create an education system that is more responsive and responsive to the needs of the times.

In the history of curriculum development in Indonesia, it has been recorded eleven times, namely since 1945, the national education curriculum has undergone changes in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1973, 1975, 1984, 1994, 1999, 2004, 2006 and 2013. Which is where Each curriculum has its advantages and disadvantages. And this curriculum can change at any time according to educational needs in Indonesia. In producing superior graduates, each curriculum should be organized and adapted to the needs of students and teachers. By studying the history of curriculum development in Indonesia, it is hoped that the government will no longer dismantle the curriculum and carry out continuous improvements but can determine the best for the nation's next generation who should be competent in the world of education.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Primary Curriculum Development History of Elementary Curriculum Development in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Khamid. 2012. History, Function and Position of the Indonesian Language. <http://abdulkhamid12.wordpress.com/bahanindonesia/materi/historiFUs-dan-kedunian-language-indonesia/>
- Abdullah Asep. 2020. History of the Indonesian Language. Journal ; UINSA Press
- Adlini, MN, Dinda, AH, Yulinda, S., Chotimah, O., Merliyana, SJ 2022. Qualitative Research Methods Literature Study. Edumaspul: Journal of Education, 6(1), 974-980.
- Affan, MH, & Maksum, H. 2016. Rebuilding the Nationalist Attitude of the Indonesian Nation in Countering Foreign Culture in the Era of Globalization. Journal of Basic Charm, 3(4), 65 - 72.
- Ananda, Putri Adelia. Jurnal perkembangan kurikulum pendidikan Indonesia dari masa ke masa. 2021, FKIP Universitas Sri Wijaya. Vol. 3, No. 2,(Juli-Desember 2021) : 102-108
- Fitri Wahyuni, Kurikulum dari masa ke masa, Jurnal, Al-Adabiya, Vol.10,no. 2, Juli-Desember 2015
- Insani, Dina Fara. Sejarah perkembangan kurikulum di Indonesia sejak awal kemerdekaan hingga saat ini. 2019, As-Salam I. Vol. VII, No. 1, Th 2019
- Sari Latur, Evi. Jurnal kurikulum di Indonesia : tinjauan perkembangan kurikulum pendidikan, STAK Anak Bangsa, Vol. 2, No. 2, Juli 2022